

Development of Bench-Scale Instrument for Testing Thermal Protective Performance in Different Orientations

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OBJECTIVES

- ❖ Develop a novel bench-scale instrument capable of testing TPP at any orientation (0° to 180°).
- ❖ Integrate advanced heat flux sensors with orientation adjustment systems.
- ❖ Validation of the instrument's measurement
- ❖ Provide comprehensive understanding of orientation impact on thermal protection.

CONCEPTUALIZATION AND PLANNING

- Heat source which mimic outside environment
- Sensor to mimic human skin
- Arrangement to change the direction
- Attachment to bring airgap
- Sample holder
- PLC based controls
- Software interface to control

BACKGROUND

- Current bench scale testing methods are limited to fixed orientations, which limits real-world scenarios
- As the orientation changes, the heat transfer changes
- When there is a significant temperature difference across the air gap, density variations cause buoyancy forces that drive convective motion.
- Gravity enters the problem through these buoyancy forces, and the effect can be quantified by dimensionless numbers such as Boussinesq approximation, Grashof and Rayleigh numbers.
- Protective performance at different orientations may bring new opportunity to redesign thermal protective clothing.

$$q_{total} = q_{conduction} + q_{convection} + q_{radiation}$$

$$q_{conv} = h \cdot A \cdot (T_1 - T_2)$$

$$h = \frac{Nu \cdot K}{L}$$

$$Nu = C \cdot (Gr \cdot Pr)^n$$

$$Rayleigh\ number\ (Ra) = Gr \cdot Pr = \frac{g\beta\Delta T d^3}{\nu\alpha}$$

INSTRUMENT

- Sample Holder**
- Size: 15×15 cm²
 - Firm holding
 - Can support fabrics with different thickness

- Air gap**
- Air gap can be provided from 0 mm to 40 mm.
 - Knob with scale for precise air gap

Heat sources

- Variable heat source
- Radiant source: Nine 500W quartz infrared lamps
- Convective source: Two Meker burners
- Protective shutter system for controlled exposure

Sensor system

- Copper calorimeter heat flux sensor
- Type J thermocouple
- Sensor weighted to 1000 ± 10 g with flat black coating (absorptivity ≥ 0.9)
- Data acquisition system with programmable logic control (PLC)

TESTING CAPABILITIES

- Orientation range: 0° to 180° rotation and heat flux of 0 to 100 kW/m²
- Variable air gap adjustment between heat source and specimen
- Automated testing sequences with safety interlocks
- Real-time data logging and burn time calculation
- Can measure second degree burn time
- Measurement of stored energy

- Pressure valve**
- Pressure control
 - Wide pressure range
 - Robust construction

- PLC system**
- Real time control
 - Data logging capabilities
 - Input/output versatility

VALIDATION

RESULTS

CONCLUSION

- Developed a novel bench-scale instrument for testing thermal protective performance at variable orientations
- The instrument can test 0 to 100 kW/m², 0 to 180 degree
- There is significant impact of orientation on heat transfer rates
- The technology transfer to industry partner
- The instrument may help in development of thermal protective clothing
- Bridged the gap between laboratory testing and real-world firefighting scenarios
- Can be used for materials other than textile
- Filed for patent

AKNOWLEDGMENT

